

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART VI. STUDY OF THE ADSORPTION OF PRECIPITATING AND STABILISING IONS BY As_2S_3 AND $Fe(OH)_3$ SOLS AT THEIR COAGULATING CONCENTRATIONS

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Simultaneous adsorption of the coagulating ion as well as of the ion carrying the same charge as the colloid has been estimated during the course of coagulation. The coagulation concentrations used during the course of the experiments have been varied with a view to studying the adsorption of the ions at different ranges of the time of coagulation.

Dhar and collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 313; 1925, 29, 434) believe that the amount of adsorption is greater, the lesser the valency of the precipitating ion, whereas Weiser and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1924, 28, 233; 1925, 29, 955; 1926, 30, 20) are of opinion that greater the valency of the precipitating ion, the greater is the adsorption.

From these views an attempt has been made to correlate adsorption with coagulation concentration. According to Dhar (*loc. cit.*) potassium with a low coagulating power is adsorbed in a larger quantity whereas bi-, and trivalent coagulating ions with greater coagulating powers are less adsorbed. This at first sight appears to be a contradiction as ions with greater adsorption have low precipitating power and *vice versa*.

In our opinion the actual amount, say, of a cation adsorbed by any negatively charged sol primarily depends on the amount of the charge that has to be neutralised, evidently K^+ ions required will be three times the number of Al^{+++} ions. If a quantity of a sol is taken which carries one faraday of electricity, then 39.10 g. of K^+ ions would be needed to neutralise the charge of the sol, whereas only 8.99 g. of Al^{+++} ions will be required. Hence if the quantity of a cation adsorbed mainly depends on charge neutralisation then the ratio of the adsorption of $K:Al$, if expressed in g. for the same quantity of the colloid, would be 39.10 : 8.99. Here it is clear that K^+ ions are certainly more adsorbed when expressed in g. These quantities may be slightly altered due to adsorption by the neutral coagulated particles, but this adsorption is so small that the relative amount adsorbed will not be markedly changed in the course of coagulation experiments, and therefore the ratio of $K:Al$ ions adsorbed, when expressed in g., will always be considerably greater than one.

This is what is exactly meant by Dhar's statement that K^+ ions are more adsorbed than Al^{+++} ions. But the coagulation concentration bears no relation to these because otherwise coagulation would have a direct numerical relation with valency *i.e.*, the concentration necessary to coagulate any sol by mono-, bi-, tri-, and tetra-valent ions should be in the ratio of $1:\frac{1}{2}:\frac{1}{3}:\frac{1}{4}$, but this is not what we find. Instead we get Wetham's law *viz*, $1::x:x^2:x^3$. This increase in the coagulating power in geometrical progression can be explained by the fact that all the ions added at the coagulation concentration are not completely adsorbed.

In the case of univalent ions the percentage adsorbed is exceedingly small whereas with multivalent ions this percentage increases. This can be easily understood because the electrostatic force between the colloidal particle and the coagulating ion increases with valency, and if the adsorption of the coagulating ion is helped by the electrostatic force then the percentage adsorbed should increase because the minimum energy necessary to enable the ion to penetrate the double layer is smaller in polyvalent ions than in monovalent ions. With the increase in percentage of the coagulating ion adsorbed there is bound to be a decrease in the coagulation concentration. Perhaps it is this increase in the percentage adsorbed from the

electrolyte which Weiser has in view when he says that greater is the valency of the precipitating ion, the greater is its adsorption.

In this paper both the actual quantity as well as the percentage adsorbed of various coagulating ions by different colloids have been investigated with a view to substantiating the above argument.

EXPERIMENTAL

As_2S_3 and $Fe(OH)_3$ sols were prepared exactly in the same manner as described in Part I of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 25). Arsenious sulphide sol has been coagulated by KCl , $BaCl_2$, and $AlCl_3$ and the adsorption of both anions and cations has been determined. Ferric hydroxide sol was coagulated by KCl , K_2SO_4 , $K_3Fe(CN)_6$, and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$; both anions and cations adsorbed have been estimated.

Both the above mentioned sols were coagulated by adding varying concentrations of the particular electrolyte in question. The highest concentration used was that which coagulated the sol in ten minutes, and the lowest was that which coagulated them in 10 to 16 days. The sol-electrolyte mixtures were left in contact till complete coagulation.

100 c.c. of the arsenious sulphide sol were taken in several glass-stoppered bottles of 200 c.c. capacity. To one set of these bottles was added $N-KCl$ in varying concentrations; the sol and the electrolyte mixtures being always made up to 200 c.c. by adding the requisite volume of distilled water to electrolyte and then mixed. Similarly $BaCl_2(N/20)$ and $AlCl_3(N/100)$ were added to the sol. In the case of ferric hydroxide sol the volume of the sol taken in each bottle was 50 c.c.; the total volume of the sol and electrolyte taken being made up to 100 c.c. The estimations of some of the ions were done gravimetrically while in the case of some of them volumetric method was used. For example K , Ba , Al and SO_4 were determined by the usual gravimetric methods while chlorine, ferricyanide and ferrocyanide ions were determined by volumetric methods by titrating chlorine against a standard solution of silver nitrate and ferri- and ferrocyanide ions against a standard solution of potassium permanganate.

Adsorption of precipitating and stabilising ions by the As_2S_3 sol Sol. conc. = 17.02 g./litre

TABLE I

$N-KCl$ added.	Time of coagulation.	K actually adsorbed.	% of K adsorbed.	K adsorbed to K equiv. of Cl adsorbed.	Cl adsorbed.	% of Cl adsorbed as fraction of Total chlorine.	K adsorbed.
16'0	10 min.	0'0297 g.	4'74 g.	0'01084	0'0171 g.	3'01	63'49
15'0	1 hrs.	0'0250	4'27	0'0078	0'0156	2'91	68'82
14'0	12 hrs.	0'0210	3'84	0'0179	0'0029	0'56	14'95
13'0	2 days	0'0184	3'62	0'0170	0'0014	0'31	7'65
12'0	4 days	0'0154	3'29	0'0149	0'00044	0'01	3'18
11'0	7 days	0'0143	3'33	0'0139	0'00039	0'009	3'01
10'0	10 days	0'0111	2'84	0'0111	0'00001	0'003	0'09

TABLE II

$N/20-BaCl_2$ added.	Time of coagulation.	Ba actually adsorbed.	% of Ba adsorbed.	Ba adsorbed to Ba equiv. of Cl adsorbed.	Cl adsorbed.	% of Cl adsorbed as fraction of Total chlorine.	Ba adsorb.
10'0 c.c.	10 min.	0'0042 g.	12'26 g.	0'0036 g.	0'00015 g.	0'88	13'84
9'0	1 hr.	0'0055	18'74	0'0049	0'00016	1'02	11'27
8'0	12	0'0058	21'17	0'0051	0'00019	1'36	12'69
7'0	7 days	0'0057	23'62	0'0049	0'00020	1'61	13'59
6'0	10	0'0060	29'18	0'0052	0'00021	1'98	13'56

TABLE III

N/100-AlCl ₃ added.	Time of coagulation.	Al actually adsorbed.	% of Al adsorbed.	Al-adsorbed to Al equiv. of Cl adsorbed.	Cl adsorbed.	% of Cl adsorbed as fraction of Total adsorb.	% of Cl adsorbed as fraction of Al adsorb.
5.0 c.c.	10 min.	0.1103 mg.	24.53	0.1085 mg.	0.0070 mg.	0.42	1.61
4.5	2 hrs.	0.1240	30.66	0.1217	0.0090	0.56	1.84
4.0	4 days	0.1866	51.88	0.1842	0.0095	0.68	1.29
3.5	8	0.2148	68.35	0.2123	0.0097	0.79	1.14
3.0	16	0.2268	84.08	0.2243	0.0099	0.94	1.11

In the following tables the adsorption of the precipitating ion as well as the stabilising ion has been determined in a ferric hydroxide sol which was dialysed.

TABLE IV

Conc. Fe₂O₃ sol = 5.024 g./litre. Chlorine content of the sol = 1.367 g./litre.

N-KCl added.	Time of coagulation.	Cl actually adsorbed.	% of Cl adsorbed.	Cl adsorbed to Cl equiv. of K adsorbed.	K adsorbed.	% of K adsorbed as fraction of Total K ads.	% of K adsorbed as fraction of Cl adsorb.
28.0 c.c.	10 min.	0.0996 g.	5.02	0.0425 g.	0.0630 g.	2.88	57.34
27.0	2 hrs.	0.0852	4.45	0.0649	0.0224	1.06	23.84
26.0	2 days	0.0789	4.28	0.0636	0.0169	0.83	19.42
25.0	7	0.0649	3.66	0.0666	0.0047	0.24	6.57

TABLE V

N/10-K ₂ SO ₄ added.	Time of coagulation.	SO ₄ actually adsorbed.	% of SO ₄ adsorbed.	SO ₄ adsorbed to SO ₄ equiv. of K adsorbed.	K adsorbed.	% of K adsorbed as fraction of Total K ads.	% of K adsorbed as fraction of SO ₄ ads.
10.0 c.c.	10 min.	0.0184 g.	76.67	0.0181 g.	0.0002 g.	1.02	1.34
8.0	2 hrs.	0.0172	69.59	0.0168	0.0003	1.93	2.14
7.0	2 days	0.0157	93.47	0.0152	0.0004	2.92	3.13
6.0	4 months.	No coagulation occurred during this period.					

TABLE VI

K ₂ Fe(CN) ₆ (0.006N) added.	Time of coagulation.	Fe(CN) ₆ actually adsorbed.	% of Fe(CN) ₆ adsorbed.	*FeX-adsorbed to FeX equiv. of K ads.	K adsorbed.	% of K adsorbed as fraction of Total K.	FeX ads.
27.5 c.c.	10 min.	9.60 mg.	82.4	9.57 mg.	0.008 g.	0.12	0.15
25.0	2 hrs.	9.62	90.8	9.58	0.012	0.20	0.225
22.5	2 days.	8.96	93.9	8.91	0.025	0.48	0.504
20.0	10 days.	8.104	95.6	8.04	0.036	0.76	0.802

TABLE VII

K ₂ Fe(CN) ₆ (0.004N) added.	Time of coagulation.	Fe(CN) ₆ actually adsorbed.	% of FeX adsorbed.	*FeX adsorbed to FeX equiv. of K ads.	K adsorbed.	% of K adsorbed as fraction of Total K.	FeX ads.
22.0 c.c.	10 min.	8.22 mg.	88.2	8.212 mg.	0.055 mg.	0.08	0.092
20.0	2 hrs.	7.84	92.5	7.827	0.0094	0.15	0.165
19.0	1 day	7.71	95.8	7.686	0.0172	0.29	0.306
18.0	7 days	7.469	97.7	7.427	0.0304	0.54	0.559

* Where X represents (CN)₆.

DISCUSSION

From the results given in column 8 of the above tables, it is clear that the same ion *e.g.*, Cl in the case of As_2S_3 sol and K in the case of Fe_2O_3 sol is differently adsorbed when different electrolytes are used for coagulation. When we take uni-univalent salts like KCl the percentage adsorption of the ion carrying the same charge as the colloid is considerable, whereas with $BaCl_2$ and K_2SO_4 the same ions are much less adsorbed. The adsorption is still less with $AlCl_3$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$. Thus there is experimental evidence that with uni-univalent salts, a considerable percentage of the coagulating ion adsorbed is due to the adsorption of similarly charged ion. When the time of coagulation is increased, the percentage of similarly charged ion decreases in the case of uni-univalent salts.

If the valency of the coagulating ion is increased the percentage adsorption increases. It also increases when the time of coagulation is increased with multivalent ions but with univalent ions it decreases. This is probably due to the decrease in the adsorption of similarly charged ion with increase of time of coagulation, as evident from the results given in column 7 of the above tables.

From the above tables the ratios of K : Ba : Al adsorbed, when expressed in moles, as well as the ratios of their coagulating concentrations are given for As_2S_3 , similarly for $Fe(OH)_3$ sol the ratios of Cl : SO_4 : $Fe(CN)_6^{III}$: $Fe(CN)_6^{IV}$ are given in the following tables. While calculating the ratios of the amount adsorbed, the values given in column 5 of the above tables are taken, as they give the amount of the coagulating ion adsorbed minus the adsorption which is equivalent to the adsorption of the ion carrying the same charge as the colloid.

TABLE VIII

 As_2S_3 sol.

Time of coagulation.	Relative moles adsorbed			Relative coagulating conc.		
	K.	Ba.	Al.	K.	Ba.	Al.
10 min.	68.9	6.5	1	320.0	10	1
2 hrs.	44.2	7.9	1	333.3	10	1
12 hrs.	66.9	5.4	1	350.0	10	1
7 days	45.2	4.5	1	314.0	10	1
10 days	34.1	4.55	1	333.3	10	1

TABLE IX

 $Fe(OH)_3$ sol.

Time of coagulation.	Relative moles adsorbed.				Relative coagulating conc.			
	Cl.	SO_4	$Fe(CN)_6^{III}$	$Fe(CN)_6^{IV}$	Cl.	SO_4	$Fe(CN)_6^{III}$	$Fe(CN)_6^{IV}$
10 min.	30.9	4.98	1.16	1	621.9	5.68	1.875	1
2 hrs.	49.55	4.73	1.22	1	675.0	5.00	1.875	1
2 days	49.46	4.36	1.16	1	684.2	4.60	1.776	1
7 days	48.77	6	1.08	1	694.5	4.167	1.567	1

From the above tables it is clear that the coagulating ions with lesser valency are adsorbed more. Moreover, the ratios are very different from 3 : 1.5 : 1 for K : Ba : Al in the case of As_2S_3 sol, whereas in the case of $Fe(OH)_3$ sol we observe that the ratios of Cl : SO_4 : $Fe(CN)_6^{III}$: $Fe(CN)_6^{IV}$ are far different from 4:2:1.33:1, which we should get if adsorption was only due to charge neutralisation. These results are in complete agreement with the work of Dhar and collaborators.

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